

TRACING THE TURMERIC TRIO UNDER THE LENS: COMPARATIVE PHARMACOGNOSTICAL EVALUATION OF RHIZOME OF *CURCUMA LONGA* (HARIDRA), *CURCUMA AMADA* (AMRAGANDHI HARIDRA), AND *CURCUMA AROMATICA* (KRISHNA HARIDRA)**S. A. Meshram^{1*}, P. K. More², S. R. Yadav³, P. P. Purohit⁴, B. V. Dhanavade⁵**

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ABSTRACT

Turmeric is an Ayurvedic drug represented by multiple species, of which *Curcuma longa* (Haridra), *Curcuma amada* (Amragandhi Haridra), and *Curcuma aromatica* (Krishna Haridra) hold significant therapeutic value. Although often used interchangeably, these spices differ in their medicinal properties, making accurate identification essential to prevent adulteration and ensure efficacy. The present study aimed to establish pharmacognostical differences among the three through macroscopic, organoleptic, and microscopic evaluations. Macroscopic examination revealed distinct characteristics: *Curcuma longa* showed bright yellow-orange rhizomes, *Curcuma amada* appeared pale yellow with a mango-like aroma, and *Curcuma aromatica* was dark brown with a camphoraceous odor. Microscopic features further differentiated them, with *Curcuma longa* presenting a thick cork and scattered vascular bundles, *Curcuma amada* showing large oil cells and spongy ground tissue, and *Curcuma aromatica* containing dense resin ducts and irregular starch grains. These observations provide reliable diagnostic markers to distinguish the species. The study emphasizes the role of pharmacognostical analysis in authenticating raw drugs, standardizing formulations, and safeguarding the therapeutic potential of *Curcuma* species in Ayurvedic practice.

KEYWORDS: *C. amada*, *C. aromatica*, *C. longa*, Pharmacognostical evaluation, Rhizome microscopy, Transverse section (T.S.).

INTRODUCTION

Turmeric, commonly referred to as *Haridra* in classical Ayurvedic literature, is a versatile herb belonging to the *Zingiberaceae* family. Its extensive usage as a dietary spice, coloring agent, and therapeutic herb is well acknowledged across cultures. Despite sharing the same family, the three main varieties- *Curcuma longa*

(*Haridra*), *Curcuma amada* (*Amragandhi Haridra*), and *Curcuma aromatica* (*Krishna Haridra*)-display considerable variations in their phytoconstituents, therapeutic uses, and organoleptic and microscopic features.

The Ayurvedic classics describe *Haridra* in *Dashemani Gana* like *Lekhaniya*,^[1] *Kandughna*,^[2] and *Vishaghna*.^[3] In Bhavprakash Nighantu, it's also mentioned as “*varnya*” (enhancer of complexion), “*Krimighna*” (anthelmintic), and “*Raktashodhak*” (blood purifier).^[4] On the other hand, *Amragandhi Haridra* or *Amada*, which smells like mango, is mainly used for external application and digestive issues.^[5] *Krishna Harida*, known for its strong aroma and deeper pigmentation, finds its usage in skin ailments and wound healing.^[6]

To prevent adulteration and promote correct usage, there is a compelling need to distinguish these rhizomes through a detailed pharmacognostical analysis, particularly by studying their T.S. (transverse section) features, as it provides reliable diagnostic microscopic markers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Collection and authentication

Rhizomes of *Curcuma longa*, *Curcuma amada*, and *Curcuma aromatica* were collected from authenticated sources and identified using botanical standards.

“Fig. 1”: Macroscopic comparison of rhizomes from three *Curcuma* species.

From left to right^[1]

- *Haridra* (*Curcuma longa*) – Bright yellow-orange rhizome with smooth surface
- *Amragandhi Haridra* (*Curcuma amada*) – Pale yellow, ginger-like rhizome
- *Krishna Haridra* (*Curcuma aromatica*) – Dark brownish rhizome

2. Macroscopic and Organoleptic Evaluation

Each rhizome was assessed for its color, size, odor, taste, and surface characteristics.

3. Microscopic (T.S.) Examination

Thin hand-cut and microscope sections of fresh rhizomes were stained using the safranin coloring agent.^[7] Sections were observed under a compound microscope, and photographic documentation was done. The features examined included cork, cortex, vascular bundles, ground tissue, oil cells, and starch grains.

RESULTS

Macroscopic Features

Macroscopic and Organoleptic characteristics of rhizomes from three *Curcuma* Species.

Table 1: Macroscopic and Organoleptic Characteristics of Rhizomes from Three *Curcuma* Species.

This table compares the external and sensory features of *Curcuma longa* (*Haridra*), *Curcuma amada* (*Amragandhi Haridra*), and *Curcuma aromatica* (*Krishna Haridra*), including their color, odor, taste, and shape, aiding in preliminary identification.

Parameter	<i>C. longa</i> (<i>Haridra</i>)	<i>C. amada</i> (<i>Amragandhi Haridra</i>)	<i>C. aromatica</i> (<i>Krishna Haridra</i>)
Color	Yellow-orange	Light yellow	Yellow to black-brown
Odor	Aromatic	Mango-like	Camphor-like
Taste	Bitter and pungent	Slightly sour, mild bitter	Strongly pungent, bitter
Shape	Irregular oblong	Ginger like with nodes	Oval, almond-shaped tips

Microscopic (T.S.) Features

Microscopic Transverse Section (T.S.) features from three *Curcuma* Species.

Table 2: Microscopic Transverse Section (T.S.) Features from Three *Curcuma* Species.

This table highlights the anatomical features observed in transverse sections of the rhizomes of *Curcuma longa* (*Haridra*), *Curcuma amada* (*Amragandhi Haridra*), and *Curcuma aromatica* (*Krishna Haridra*), including cork layer thickness, vascular bundle pattern, oil cell distribution, presence of resin ducts, and starch grain morphology.

Features	<i>C. longa</i> (<i>Haridra</i>)	<i>C. amada</i> (<i>Amragandhi Haridra</i>)	<i>C. aromatica</i> (<i>Krishna Haridra</i>)
Cork	4-6 layers, thick, brown	4-5 layers, compact	Thick, multiple layers, brown
Cortex	Parenchymatous, oil cells	Spongy, large starch grains	Dense, resin ducts present
Vascular bundles	Scattered, collateral	Fewer, loosely scattered	Compact and numerous
Ground tissue	Compact, with oil globules	Spongy with volatile oil cells	Resinous, strongly aromatic
Starch grains	Oval/round, abundant	Larger, round	Numerous, irregular
Oil cells	Moderate	Large and abundant	Dense with camphor scent

Microscopic Transverse Sections (T.S.) of Rhizomes

The following figures illustrate the transverse sections of the three *Curcuma* species, highlighting diagnostic microscopic features such as cork structure, oil cells, starch grains, and resin ducts.

“Fig 2”: T.S. of *Curcuma longa* (*Haridra*) rhizome showing thick cork, scattered vascular bundles, and parenchymatous ground tissue with moderate oil cells and abundant starch grains.

“Fig 3:” T.S. of *Curcuma amada* (*Amragandhi Haridra*) rhizome highlighting compact cork layers, spongy cortex with large starch grains, and abundant oil cells indicating high volatile content.

Fig. 4: T.S. of *Curcuma aromatica* (*Krishna Haridra*) rhizome exhibiting thick brown cork, numerous compact vascular bundles, and distinct resin ducts with irregular starch grains.

DISCUSSION

The comparison reveals distinct features that help in the pharmacognostical identification of each rhizome.

- ***Curcuma longa*:** Known for high curcumin, it shows a typical parenchymatous cortex, well-developed cork, and scattered vascular bundles. The starch grains are numerous and small, while oil cells are moderate.
- ***Curcuma amada*:** Notable for its unique mango aroma, *Amragandhi Haridra* has a spongy cortex and larger starch grains. The oil cells are more prominent, suggesting their volatile oil content and aromatic nature.
- ***Curcuma aromatica*:** *Krishna Haridra* is characterized by its dark pigmentation, strong smell, and thick cork. The resin ducts, circular nodes, and irregular starch grains are unique identifiers. These features support its potent wound healing and skin care properties.

Image analysis

- The transverse sections clearly show a difference in cork and vascular bundle arrangement.

- The ground tissue density and resin duct visibility in *Krishna Haridra* are noticeably higher.
- Oil cells in *Amragandhi Haridra* appear more widespread, explaining its aromatic and topical use.

Therapeutic Significance and Usage

Therapeutic significance and usage of three *Curcuma* species.

Table No. 3: Therapeutic significance and usage of three *Curcumin* species.

This table shows the therapeutic significance and usage of *Curcuma longa* (*Haridra*), *Curcuma amada* (*Amragandhi Haridra*), and *Curcuma aromatica* (*Krishna Haridra*).

Species	Key Dosha Action	Therapeutic Indications	Matra (Dose)
<i>Curcuma longa</i>	<i>Kapha-pitta shamak</i>	Skin disorders, wounds, diabetes, liver disorders ^[8]	2-4 gm
<i>Curcuma amada</i>	<i>Vata-pitta hara</i>	Anti-inflammatory, itching, digestive issues ^[9]	2-4 gm
<i>Curcuma aromatica</i>	<i>Kapha-pitta shamak</i>	Acne, eczema, fungal infections, blood disorders ^[10]	1-2 gm

Additional Traditional Uses

- *Haridra Khanda*: Used in eczema, urticarial.^[11]
- *Amada lepa*: Applied to itches and wounds.^[9]
- *Krishna Haridra Taila*: Topical oil for fungal and bacterial infections.^[12]
- *Haridra* is used in many formulations of decoction in the treatment of *Prameha* along with *Amalaki*.^[13]

CONCLUSION

The detailed pharmacognostical and microscopic comparison of the rhizomes of *Curcuma longa*, *Curcuma amada*, and *Curcuma aromatica* underscores the importance of correct species identification in *Ayurvedic* formulations. While macroscopically similar, these species exhibit key differences in transverse section structure, including cork layering, vascular bundles, and oil cells, that serve as diagnostic tools. Correct identification ensures therapeutic efficacy, prevents adulteration, and enhances pharmacovigilance in herbal drug use.

Further analytical studies like HPTLC and DNA barcoding can complement these findings for robust authentication.

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